

Dual-hop Blockchain Radio Access Networks for Advanced Coverage Expansion

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Abstract—Dynamic dual-hop relaying network topologies that enable access to end-users through intermediate individual and commercial, static as well as moving, infrastructures are expected to become fundamental pillars of the sixth generation wireless systems. Their main requirement is to ensure end-user's information privacy. Motivated by this, the current contribution focuses on introducing a dual-hop blockchain radio access network (DH-BRAN) topology for dynamic coverage expansion. To analyze the performance of this topology, we present the theoretical framework that captures its characteristics. Building upon it, the DH-BRAN performance, in terms of latency and waiting probability, are quantified. Our results reveal that DR-BRAN can be employed in several realistic use-cases and that there exists a trade-off between latency and security.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Coverage Expansion, Dual-hop relaying, Latency, Privacy, Radio access networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blockchain has been identified as a disruptive innovation shockwave [1]–[3], which, according to the federated communications commission (FDD) [4], its integration in the sixth generation (6G) wireless networks will boost their security and privacy capabilities. As a result, a new concept is created, namely blockchain radio access network (B-RAN), that is envisioned to transform conventional networks into intelligent platforms, which enable secure decentralized wireless access through both untrusted individual and commercial infrastructures, allowing rights, responsibilities and obligations of each participant to be flexibly translated to smart contracts, while guaranteeing high level of privacy [5].

Inspired by this, several researchers investigated the integration of blockchain in different parts of the network (see e.g., [6], [7] and reference therein). An indicative example was reported in [8], where the authors presented a blockchain-based spectrum sharing mechanism that allows collaboration by means of smart contracts between untrusted network operators that share the same frequency channels. Additionally, in [9], the authors highlighted some critical issues for the blockchain application in wireless networks. The application of blockchain in order to enable infrastructure sharing among different network providers was explored in [10]. Meanwhile, in [11], the authors investigated the use of blockchain to support secure task offloading between user equipments (UEs) and edge nodes. Another interesting application of blockchain was introduced in [5], where the authors introduced the concept of B-RAN and enumerated its multiple positive impact that may

bring to next generation wireless networks. An in-lab experimental prototype that verified the feasibility and effectiveness of B-RAN was reported in [12]. This prototype revealed that the inter-time between two requests at the blockchain, the generation of two consecutive blocks, and the service time are independent stochastic processes that follow exponential distributions. Building upon this observation, in [13], presented a Markov-chain based theoretical framework that accommodates the particularities of B-RAN. Importantly, their results highlighted the relation between latency and security.

In spite of privacy and security, another key requirement of 6G wireless networks is high coverage [14]–[16]. To enhance coverage and provide cell expansion, the third generation partnership project (3GPP) proposed the use of relays that belong to the same service provider [17]–[20]. However, the ownership limitation may increase the network deployment cost and also create coverage holes [21]. Motivated by this as well as the advantages of B-RAN, in this paper, we introduce a novel network architecture that we name dual-hop B-RAN (DH-BRAN), that enables individual and commercial intermediate nodes to become wireless access providers independently of their ownership. DR-BRAN employs two blockchains, i.e., the primary and the secondary. The secondary blockchain is used to provide access to the end-user through an ad-hoc network that consists of a number of different individual and/or commercial secondary miner. After verifying the request, the intermediate node forwards it to the primary blockchain. This process guarantees high-security and privacy at a cost of latency. In order to assess its feasibility and efficiency, we present an analytical queuing model, based on time-homogeneous Markov processes. Building upon this model, we conduct respective Monte Carlo simulations that quantify the DH-BRAN performance in terms of latency and delay probability. For the sake of comparison, the results are compared against the case in which the end user is directly connected to the primary B-RAN.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the topology of DH-BRAN and the proposed protocol steps. Section II is focused on providing a low-complexity Markov-based model that captures the particularities of DH-BRAN, while, Section III reports the performance of DH-BRAN by means of Monte Carlo simulations. Finally, Section V summarizes this contribution by reporting our main findings and remarks.

Fig. 1: Network topology

II. NETWORK TOPOLOGY

As illustrated in Fig. 1, we consider a network topology that consists of several access points (APs) that belong to the same or different service providers (SPs), and a massive number of user equipments (UEs). The UEs can access the network either directly, i.e., through an AP, or indirectly, i.e., by employing another intermediate UE (IUE), which is already connected to an AP. For clarity, we define two type of networks, namely primary and secondary. In the primary one, UEs can directly connect to an AP, while, in the secondary network, they employ an IUE. In order to ensure high-level of security and privacy, B-RAN protocols are applied in both the primary and secondary networks. Each network creates its own blockchain in order to create trust between the different SPs. The primary B-RAN uses as miner both APs and UEs, while the secondary one, only UEs with relatively high computational capabilities. Primary and secondary B-RANs cooperate with each other in order to provide access to out-of-coverage UEs.

This work is devoted on dual-hop B-RAN based advanced coverage expansion for which the procedure is described in Fig. 2, given at the top of the following page. In more detail, it consists of eight steps:

- In step 1, the out-of-coverage UE makes an access request at the IUE. The request is recorded to a smart contract in order to create a service level agreement (SLA) among the two parts. Then, the smart contract is committed to the secondary B-RAN mining and verified by its miners.
- In step 2, the verified smart contract is included into the next block, which is generated by the secondary B-RAN. The new block is appended at the end of the secondary blockchain, in order for the request to receive its first confirmation.
- In step 3, the block containing the request receives the minimum required confirmations, in order to be accepted at the secondary main chain. This occurs after the gener-

ation of $M - 1$ secondary blocks.

- In step 4, IUE makes an access request to the official AP at which is connected. This request is recorded to another smart contract, which is committed at the primary B-RAN in order to define the SLA among the AP and IUE.
- In step 5, the generated smart contract is assembled into a primary block, following the workflow of step 2, at the primary B-RAN this time.
- In step 6, the new block is appended into the primary chain after receiving $N - 1$ confirmations (primary block generations).
- In step 7, in the case in which there is no available access resource at primary network, the confirmed request enters to a waiting for service queue.
- In step 8, UE accesses the network through the IUE. The access terms are specified by the smart contracts signed at primary and secondary networks.

III. MARKOV-CHAIN BASED BH-RAN MODELING

In DH-BRAN, primary and secondary B-RANs can be viewed as a united system that can be modeled using queuing theory. The state of this system, at any time t , can be described as a vector

$$X(t) = E(j_0, j_1, \dots, j_{M-1}, i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}, k), \quad (1)$$

where j_m and i_n are the numbers of requests with m confirmations at the secondary network and n confirmations at primary network respectively. The number of confirmed requests waiting for service is denoted by k .

It can be proved, by the analytical workflow of [13], that request arrivals, primary and secondary block generations, as well as service completions follow the Poisson distribution, with rates λ_a , λ_{b_1} , λ_{b_2} , and λ_c , respectively. The corresponding times are exponential, with rates

$$\mu_a = \frac{1}{\lambda_a}, \quad \mu_{b_1} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{b_1}}, \quad \mu_{b_2} = \frac{1}{\lambda_{b_2}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_c = \frac{1}{\lambda_c}. \quad (2)$$

The time until the next event occurrence, for all the four aforementioned events, is also exponential with rate

$$\lambda = \lambda_a + \lambda_{b_1} + \lambda_{b_2} + \lambda_c. \quad (3)$$

During the interval $(t, t + h)$, where $h \rightarrow 0$, one or none of that events can occur, while the probability for two or more simultaneous occurrences tends to zero. Thus, the queuing model $X(t)$ can be characterized as a time-homogeneous Markov process.

The state transition graph of the united system is shown in Fig. 3. By assuming that the network state at time t is

$$X(t) = E_i(j_0, j_1, \dots, j_{M-1}, i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}, k), \quad (4)$$

its state at time $t + h$, where $h \rightarrow 0$, can be one of the following:

- If one UE requests access at the secondary network, so there is one more unconfirmed request in it; then,

$$X(t+h) = E(j_0 + 1, j_1, \dots, j_{M-1}, i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}, k). \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2: DH-BRAN protocol

Fig. 3: State transition graph.

The probability of this case is

$$p_a = \lambda_a h. \quad (6)$$

- If one block is generated at the primary B-RAN. All requests in it take one more confirmation, so there are not unconfirmed requests in it. Requests with $N - 1$ confirmations at time t can be served at time $t + h$. The state of the secondary network does not change. As a consequence,

$$X(t+h) = E(j_0, j_1, \dots, j_{M-1}, 0, i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1+k}). \quad (7)$$

The probability of this case is

$$p_{b_1} = \lambda_{b_1} h. \quad (8)$$

- If one block generation occurs at the secondary network, so every request in it receives one extra confirmation and there are not unconfirmed requests in it. If there are requests that just have received the M confirmation, an intermediate access request is made from the secondary to primary network in order to provide access to all devices that their requests just confirmed. Hence,

$$X(t+h) = E(0, j_0, j_1, \dots, j_{M-2}, i_0 + j_{M-1}, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}, k). \quad (9)$$

The probability of this case is

$$p_{b_2} = \lambda_{b_2} h. \quad (10)$$

- If the service of one request (at primary network) is completed, with probability

$$p_c = \lambda_c h. \quad (11)$$

So, the number of requests in service at time $t + h$ is one less than at time t . Thus,

$$X(t+h) = E(j_0, j_1, \dots, j_{M-1}, i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}, k-1). \quad (12)$$

Of note, service completion can occur only if there are requests in service at time t .

- Finally, the network remains at the same state, i.e.,

$$X(t+h) = X(t), \quad (13)$$

with probability

$$p_o = 1 - \lambda h. \quad (14)$$

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This section is focused on presenting simulation results showing the efficiency of the DH-BRAN. The key performance indicators (KPIs) that are used to evaluate the network's efficiency are latency, L , and waiting probability, P . As latency, we define the time interval between the arrival of a request and the moment in which an access link of the network is allocated to serve it. Of note, in what follows, we measure latency in terms of averaged service time. The waiting probability returns the probability of no-zero waiting time. It is important to study these KPIs at different traffic intensities, which can be obtained as

$$\rho = \frac{\lambda_a}{s\lambda_c}, \quad (15)$$

where s is the number of available access links. Note that the block spreading delay and the delay for the direct communication between the UE and IUE as well as IUE and AP are small enough to neglect.

The examine three insightful scenarios of different traffic intensities are investigated. In more detail, we set $\rho = 0.1$, $\rho = 0.4$ and $\rho = 0.7$ for low, medium and high traffic intensities, respectively. Unless otherwise stated, at both the primary and the secondary B-RAN, the block generation rate is set to 30 and the minimum number of required confirmations is 2, while, the number of available access links at the primary network is set to 5. As a benchmark, the corresponding KPIs for the case of direct access (DA), in which the UE is located within the coverage area of the primary network, is presented.

Figure 4 illustrates the impact of the number of the required request confirmations (N) to latency (L), for both cases of DA and intermediate access (IA). We set the same N for the primary and the secondary network. For a given traffic intensity ρ , we observe that as N increases, latency also increases. For example, for the case of DA and $\rho = 0.4$, as N shifts from 1 to 4, latency increases from 0.04 to 0.14, while for the same ρ variation, the latency in the IA case increases from 0.07 to 0.27. Additionally, for a fixed N , latency increase as ρ increases. For instance, for $N = 5$, as ρ increases from 0.1 to 0.7, latency changes from 0.17 to 0.26, in the case of DA, while, in the case of IA, the same ρ shift, cause a latency increase from 0.33 to 0.42. Finally, comparing DA and IA cases, we observe that for the same ρ and N , IA experience higher latency. This is because the request must be confirmed twice, i.e., both in the secondary and in the primary network.

Figure 5 depicts the relation between the number of available access links (s) and latency (L), for both cases of DA and IA. From this figure, it becomes evident that, for a fixed ρ ,

Fig. 4: The impact of minimum confirmation number on service latency for different traffic intensities.

Fig. 5: The impact of available access links on service latency, for different levels of traffic intensity.

the increment of s , results to the a corresponding reduction of L . As an example, for $\rho = 0.7$, as s increases from 1 to 9, L is reduced from 2.43 to 0.09, in the case of DA, while, in the case of IA, the same s increase results to a 2.31 latency reduction. This is due to the fact that as s increases, the number of requests that can be contemporary served increases; hence, the length of the waiting queue decreases and the probability for the queue to be empty also increases. Additionally, we observe that beyond a certain increase of s , L becomes approximately constant. Moreover, for a given s , as ρ increases, latency also increases, for both cases of DA and IA. Finally, for fixed s and ρ , we observe that IA experience higher latency than DA. For example, for $\rho = 0.1$ and $s = 1$, L is equal to 0.18, in the DA case, while, for the same ρ and s , L is 0.24, in the IA case.

Fig. 6: Waiting probability vs available access links for different levels of traffic intensity.

Figure 6 quantifies the dependency between the number of available access links and the waiting probability (p), for both cases of DA and IA. From this figure, it can be observed that for a fixed value of ρ , increasing the value of s results in lower p , for both cases of DA and IA. For example, for $\rho = 0.4$, as s shifts from 1 to 4, p decreases from approximately 0.4 to 0.03, for both DA and IA. Likewise, for a given s , as ρ increases, p also increases. For instance, in the DA case, for $s = 3$, p increases from 0.00374 to 0.49811, as ρ shifts from 0.1 to 0.7. On the contrary, for the IA case, the same ρ variation, result to a p shift from 0.00384 to 0.4929. This indicates that for given ρ and s , p is approximately the same for both cases of DA and IA.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper was focused on presenting a DH-BRAN that is expected to enable dynamic coverage expansion. Moreover, a Markov-based model was introduced that captures the particularities of such networks and allow its performance assessment. Building upon this, we evaluated its performance for three insightful scenarios of different traffic intensity in terms of latency and waiting probability. Our results, revealed that by increasing the number of access links, we can achieve similar results in terms of latency and waiting probability as in conventional B-RANs. This reveals that under careful design DH-BRAN can potentially become a high-privacy advanced coverage expansion enabler.

REFERENCES

[1] F. Tschorsch and B. Scheuermann, "Bitcoin and beyond: A technical survey on decentralized digital currencies," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 2084–2123, 2016.

[2] J. Xie, H. Tang, T. Huang, F. R. Yu, R. Xie, J. Liu, and Y. Liu, "A survey of blockchain technology applied to smart cities: Research issues and challenges," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 2794–2830, 2019.

[3] Y. Dai, D. Xu, S. Maharjan, Z. Chen, Q. He, and Y. Zhang, "Blockchain and deep reinforcement learning empowered intelligent 5g beyond," *IEEE Network*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 10–17, may 2019.

[4] Cisco Visual Networking Index, "Global mobile data traffic forecast update 2016-2021," White Paper, Feb. 2017.

[5] X. Ling, J. Wang, T. Bouchoucha, B. C. Levy, and Z. Ding, "Blockchain radio access network (b-RAN): Towards decentralized secure radio access paradigm," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 9714–9723, Jan. 2019.

[6] D. C. Nguyen, P. N. Pathirana, M. Ding, and A. Seneviratne, "Blockchain for 5G and beyond networks: A state of the art survey," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 166, p. 102693, Sep. 2020.

[7] M. Tahir, M. H. Habaebi, M. Dabbagh, A. Mughees, A. Ahad, and K. I. Ahmed, "A review on application of blockchain in 5G and beyond networks: Taxonomy, field-trials, challenges and opportunities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 115 876–115 904, Jun. 2020.

[8] M. B. H. Weiss, K. Werbach, D. C. Sicker, and C. E. C. Bastidas, "On the application of blockchains to spectrum management," *IEEE Trans. on Cogn. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 193–205, Jun. 2019.

[9] P.-H. Kuo, A. Mourad, and J. Ahn, "Potential applicability of distributed ledger to wireless networking technologies," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 4–6, Aug. 2018.

[10] B. Mafakheri, T. Subramanya, L. Goratti, and R. Riggio, "Blockchain-based infrastructure sharing in 5g small cell networks," in *14th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, Rome, Italy, Dec. 2018, pp. 313–317.

[11] X. Xu, Y. Chen, X. Zhang, Q. Liu, X. Liu, and L. Qi, "A blockchain-based computation offloading method for edge computing in 5g networks," *Software: Practice and Experience*, Sep. 2019.

[12] Y. Le, X. Ling, J. Wang, and Z. Ding, "Prototype design and test of blockchain radio access network," in *IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*. Shanghai, China: IEEE, May 2019.

[13] X. Ling, Y. Le, J. Wang, Z. Ding, and X. Gao, "Practical modeling and analysis of blockchain radio access network," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, pp. 1–1, 2020.

[14] K. Latva-aho, Matti; Leppänen, "Key drivers and research challenges for 6g ubiquitous wireless intelligence," University of Oulu, resreport, Sep. 2019.

[15] A.-A. A. Boulogeorgos, A. Alexiou, T. Merkle, C. Schubert, R. Elschner, A. Katsiotis, P. Stavrianos, D. Kritharidis, P. K. Chartsias, J. Kokkonniemi, M. Juntti, J. Lehtomäki, A. Teixeira, and F. Rodrigues, "Terahertz technologies to deliver optical network quality of experience in wireless systems beyond 5G," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 144–151, Jun. 2018.

[16] A.-A. A. Boulogeorgos, A. Alexiou, D. Kritharidis, A. Katsiotis, G. Ntouni, J. Kokkonniemi, J. Lehtomaki, M. Juntti, D. Yankova, A. Mokhtar, J.-C. Point, J. Machodo, R. Elschner, C. Schubert, T. Merkle, R. Ferreira, F. Rodrigues, and J. Lima, "Wireless terahertz system architectures for networks beyond 5G," TERRANOVA CONSORTIUM, White paper 1.0, Jul. 2018.

[17] C. Hoymann, W. Chen, J. Montojo, A. Golitschek, C. Koutsimanis, and X. Shen, "Relaying operation in 3gpp LTE: challenges and solutions," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 156–162, Feb. 2012.

[18] M. Mokhtar, A.-A. A. Boulogeorgos, G. K. Karagiannidis, and N. Al-Dhahir, "OFDM opportunistic relaying under joint transmit/receive I/Q imbalance," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 62, no. 5, pp. 1458–1468, May 2014.

[19] A.-A. A. Boulogeorgos and A. Alexiou, "Error analysis of mixed THz-RF wireless systems," *IEEE Commun. Lett.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 277–281, Feb. 2020.

[20] —, "Outage probability analysis of THz relaying systems," in *IEEE 31st Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*. IEEE, aug 2020.

[21] A.-A. A. Boulogeorgos, S. Goudos, and A. Alexiou, "Users association in ultra dense THz networks," in *IEEE International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, Kalamata, Greece, Jun. 2018.